

THE DIFFICULTIES IN TRANSLATION MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES

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Abstract. Main goal of translation for writing this article is being familiar with the translation of medical terminologies and spreading the most medical books' translations in Uzbek language. People may find their translation in Russian and other languages, in these case it creates many difficulties for medical university students.

Introduction

The translation of medical terminologies presents a unique set of challenges that require specialized knowledge, linguistic precision, and cultural sensitivity. Medical language is complex and highly specialized, with technical terms often derived from Greek, Latin, or other languages. Accurate translation is paramount to ensure the proper delivery of healthcare services and avoid potential misunderstandings or misinterpretations.

DISCUSSION THE IMPORTANT PROBLEM

Medical texts often lack the context that is present in spoken conversations. Translators must rely on their specialized knowledge to fill in missing information and understand the intended meaning of terms. This can be especially challenging when dealing with ambiguous or figurative language.

Medical concepts and practices vary significantly across cultures. Translators must be aware of cultural differences in medical terminology, such as the use of euphemisms or idioms that may not have direct equivalents in the target language.

The field of medicine is constantly evolving, leading to the introduction of new terms and concepts. Translators must stay abreast of these changes and have access to updated medical dictionaries and resources.

Medical translations require a high degree of precision to avoid confusion or errors. Translators must ensure that technical terms are accurately rendered and that the overall meaning is conveyed correctly. Consistency is also crucial to maintain uniformity throughout the translated text.

Medical translations involve sensitive information about patients and their health. Translators must adhere to ethical guidelines and maintain confidentiality. Additionally, they must be aware of any legal requirements or regulations related to the translation of medical documents.

I translated the instruction: "Epidemiology, prophylaxis and epidemiological control of quarantine and extremely dangerous infections" from Uzbek into English language. I want to share the context from translation process in order to compering both of them would be easy.

I share my own translation about the pneumonic plague diagnosing process translation:

Uzbek language	English language
O'pka o'lati. Birlamchi o'pka o'latida inkubatsiya davri 2-3 kuni tashkil etadi, bu istimaning keskin ko'tarilishi, titroq, taxikardiya, ko'krak qafasidagi og'riq va bosh og'rig'i bilan kechib, ko'pincha og'irlashadi. Dastlab ko'rinmaydigan yo'tal 24 soat ichida rivojlanadi, balg'am, avval shilimshiq bilan so'ngra qon bilan aralashib	Pneumonic plague. In primary pneumonic plague, the incubation period is 2-3 days, which is often aggravated by fever, chills, tachycardia, chest pain, and headache. An initially invisible cough develops within 24 hours, and sputum begins to appear, first mixed with mucus and then with blood, later becoming a uniform pink or light red

<p>paydo bo‘la boshlaydi, keyinchalik bir xil pushti yoki och qizil rangga (malina geliga o‘xshash) va ko‘piksimon ko‘rinishda bo‘ladi. Taxipniya va nafas qisilishi mavjud, ammo plevritli ko‘krak og‘rig‘i yo‘q bo‘ladi. Kokrak qafasi siqilishi kam uchraydi, xirillash bo‘lmasligi mumkin. Ikkilamchi o‘pka o‘lati birlamchi darajaga qaraganda ko‘p uchraydi va mikroorganizmlarning gubogen yoki boshqa infeksiya o‘choqlaridan gematogen tarqalishi natijasidir. Davolanmagan o‘pka o‘lati bilan kasallangan bemorlarning ko‘pi simptom paydo bo‘lganidan keyin 48 soat ichida vafot etadi.</p>	<p>color (similar to raspberry jelly) and foamy. Tachypnea and shortness of breath are present, but chest pain with pleurisy is absent. Chest tightness is rare, and wheezing may be absent. Secondary pneumonic plague is more common than primary and is the result of hematogenous spread of microorganisms from a bubonic or other source of infection. Most patients with untreated pneumonic plague die within 48 hours after symptom onset.</p>
<p>Uzbek language</p>	<p>English language</p>
<p>O‘latni tashxislash. Bo‘yash, bakposev, serologik tahlil va PCR</p> <p>Tashxis bo‘yash va posev bilan tasdiqlanadi, odatda bubon biopsiyasi orqali (jarrohlik drenaj kasallikni organizmga yoyishi mumkin); qon va balg‘am posevi ham qilinishi kerak.</p> <p>Boshqa testlarga immunofloescent bo‘yash va serologik testlar kiradi; PCR tahlilini qilish imkoni bo‘lsa u ham diagnostik hisoblanadi.</p> <p>Oldingi emlash o‘lat kasalligini istisno etmaydi; klinik kasallik emlangan odamlarda ham o‘zini namoyon qilishi mumkin.</p> <p>O‘pka o‘lati alomatlari bo‘lgan bemorlarda ko‘krak qafasi rentgenogrammasini zudlik bilan o‘tkazish kerak. Ko‘plab pishmagan neytrofillar bo‘lgan qondagi leykotsitlar soni odatda 10,000-20,000 / mL ni tashkil qiladi.</p>	<p>Plague diagnosis. Staining, smear, serological analysis and PCR</p> <p>Diagnosis is confirmed by staining and smear, usually by bubo biopsy (surgical drainage can spread the disease throughout the body); blood and sputum smear should be done.</p> <p>Other tests include immunofluorescent staining and serological tests; If PCR analysis is possible, it is also diagnostic.</p> <p>Previous vaccination does not exclude plague; clinical disease may also occur in vaccinated individuals.</p> <p>A ribcage radiography should be taken immediately in patients with symptoms of pneumonic plague. The number of leukocytes in the blood with many neutrophils is usually 10,000-20,000/ml.</p>

I met with difficulty of translation name of diseases, equipments and chemical processes. For the translation medical terminology book you have a base of words related to medicina. I want to say about the similarity of latin language and English, it creates somehow opportunities to the translation process.

<p>Uzbek Language</p>	<p>English Language</p>
<p>Kuydirgi bo‘yicha noxush turg‘un punktlarni hisobga olish va xaritaga tushirish (kartografiya).</p>	<p>Monitoring and mapping (cartography) of anthrax hotspots.</p> <p>Vaccination of agricultural and domestic</p>

<p>Noxush turg'un punktlardagi qishloq xo'jalik va uy hayvonlarini yoppasiga kuydirgi kasalligiga qarshi emlash.</p> <p>Noxush turg'un punktlarda sog'lomlashtiruvchi meliorativ va agrotexnika tadbirlarini o'tkazish, suv havzalarini ifloslanishdan saqlash.</p> <p>Teri tayyorlash, saqlash, tashish. va qayta ishlash jarayonlarida veterinariya- sanitariya qoidalariga amal qilish.</p> <p>Hayvonlarni so'yilishini markazlashgaya holda qushxonalarda tashkil etish, xonadonlarda so'yilishiga qat'iyon yo'l qo'ymaslik, mollarni majburiy so'yilishining oldini olish.</p> <p>Hayvonlar o'rtasida kuydirgi kasalligini o'z vaqtida aniqlash, kasal hayvonlarni boshqa hayvonlardan ajratish, o'choqlarda epizootologo-epidemiologik tekshiruvlar o'tkazish, o'lgan hayvonlarni yuqumsizlantirish va ko'mishni to'g'ri tashkil etish, o'choqlarda joriy va yakunlovchi dezinfektsiya tadbirlarini o'tkazish.</p> <p>Kuydirgi kasalligining yuqish xavfi yuqori bo'lgan aholi guruhini kuydirgiga qarshi emlash.</p> <p>8 Aholi o'rtasida kuydirgi kasalligidan saqlanish bo'yicha keng ko'lamda sanitariya-targ'ibot ishlarini o'tkazish. Kasal hayvon bilan muloqotda bo'lgan hayvonlarga zudlik bilan kuydirgiga qarshi zardob yuboriladi, keyin kuydirgiga qarshivaktsina bilan emlashga jalb etiladi. Kasal hayvon yotgan bino (ayvon) yaxshilab tozalanadi, taxta pollari olinib, pollarni tagidagi tuproqqa 20 foizli xlorli ohak eritmasiyordamida ishlov beriladi, so'ngra 15 sm qalinlikdagi tuproq qazib olinib, maxsus transportlarda mollar qabriga (skotomogil`nik) olib borib ko'miladi. O'lgan hayvon terisi bilan birga maxsus o'chokda yoqib yuboriladi. Yilning aprel-oktyabr oylarida kuydirgi bo'yicha noxush statsionar punktlaridan jadval asosida tashqi muhitdan namunalar olinib tekshirilib boriladi.</p>	<p>animals against anthrax disease in unpleasant stagnant areas.</p> <p>Carrying out remedial and agrotechnical activities in unpleasant stagnant areas, protecting water bodies from pollution.</p> <p>Skin preparation, storage, transportation. and compliance with veterinary-sanitary rules in processing processes.</p> <p>Organization of slaughtering of animals centrally in aviaries, strictly not allowing slaughtering in households, prevention of forced slaughtering of cattle.</p> <p>Timely detection of anthrax disease among animals, separation of sick animals from other animals, conducting epizootological-epidemiological examinations in the herds, proper organization of disinfection and burial of dead animals, conducting current and final disinfection measures in the herds.</p> <p>Vaccination against anthrax of the population group at high risk of infection.</p> <p>Carrying out large-scale sanitary-propaganda work on prevention of anthrax among the population. Animals that have been in contact with an infected animal are immediately given anti-anthrax serum and then encouraged to receive the anthrax vaccine. The building (porch) where the sick animal is lying is thoroughly cleaned, the wooden floors are removed, the soil under the floors is treated with a 20 percent chlorine lime solution, then a 15 cm thick soil is dug up and taken to the cattle grave (skotomogil`nik) in special vehicles and buried. The dead animal is burned along with its skin in a special furnace. In April-October of the year, samples from the external environment are taken and checked based on the schedule from the stationary stations for anthrax.</p>
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In addition, there are many books that have a demand translation of them such as Netter anatomy atlas, Memorix anatomy, Greys anatomy Rabustva anatomy and Sobotto that were written by . I give sample information about Sobotto:

Sobotta - More than just an Atlas: Learn, Understand and Test your Knowledge

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Presented in a practical package combining all three atlas volumes, covering the entire regional anatomy of the human body, as well as, a study book containing Tables of Muscles, Joints and Nerves.

The 16th edition introduces the brand new Sobotta Study Loop. A deeper focus on clinical relevance and actively supporting students prepare for medical exams makes the Sobotta - Atlas of Anatomy more relevant than ever.

In 1,300 pages the atlas offers even more insights into the human body, 500 new exam questions to help consolidate learning and support exam preparation, as well as, a guiding hand to medical students new to the subject.

To ensure accurate and reliable medical terminology translation, it is essential to follow these best practices:

1. Use specialized translators: Engage translators with a thorough understanding of medical terminology and the relevant field of medicine.
2. Provide context: Include background information and relevant documents to provide translators with the necessary context.
3. Establish a glossary: Create a comprehensive glossary of medical terms to ensure consistency throughout the translation.
4. Consider cultural differences: Be mindful of cultural variations in medical concepts and practices to avoid misunderstandings.
5. Collaborate with medical experts: Consult with medical professionals to verify the accuracy of translations and address any technical uncertainties.

CONCLUSION

By addressing the challenges to these best practices, translators can effectively convey medical terminologies across linguistic and cultural barriers, facilitating better healthcare outcomes and fostering global collaboration in the medical field.

REFERENCES

1. Medical terminology of diseases history.
2. PubMed: A comprehensive database of biomedical and life sciences literature.
3. MEDLINE: A subset of PubMed that includes indexed citations and abstracts.
4. Cochrane Library: A collection of systematic reviews and other evidence-based health information.